

Prostate cancer patient cases (diagnosis images and clinical data) for the training and validation of AI models

ID: 97c6494a-e42c-47d6-83f7-76cda5865350

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/97c6494a-e42c-47d6-83f7-76cda5865350/details>

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Contact info.: None

Studies count: 1149

Subjects count: 1149

Age range: Between 46 years and 965 years

Sex: Male

Body part(s): PROSTATE, ARM, PELVIS, ABDOMEN, Pelvis^Masculin, HEAD, ABDOMENPELVIS, PANCREAS, BRAIN, SKULL, CHESTABDPELVIS, CERVIX, KNEE, HIP, NECK, Unknown

Modality: MR, CT, DX, Unknown